

A detailed study of charge recombination dynamics in dye sensitized solar cells based on two triphenylamine based dyes

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Sustainable energy is going to be a more crucial problem than any other that we have. Solar energy is the most abundant and primary source of renewable energy that we can depend upon for our growing energy needs. Thus harvesting solar energy using photovoltaics has become a priority research area in physics and chemistry for the last several decades. Dye sensitized solar cells (DSSC) have emerged as a potential alternative to silicon based solar cells. Low production costs and environmental issues have prompted a search for metal-free organic sensitizers as alternatives for polypyridyl ruthenium(II) derivatives. Understanding the charge transfer dynamics in dye-sensitized solar cells (DSCs) is imperative for the development of highly efficient devices. Here we fabricated Γ/I_3^- electrolyte based dye-sensitized solar cells with two novel branched starburst shaped triphenylamine dyes TPAA4 and TPAA5 with broader absorption and higher molar extinction coefficient, which showed power conversion efficiencies of 6.52% and 4.60% respectively. Both the dyes were structurally engineered in such a way to avoid the recombination of electrons from TiO_2 . Detailed charge transfer dynamics of the devices were studied by employing extensive perturbation techniques such as electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (EIS), charge extraction (CE) and intensity-modulated photovoltage spectroscopic (IMVS) methods.

Key words: **EIS, Triphenyl amine dyes, Charge recombination**

References

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